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Dimitra Vangeli
Philologist MA, School of
Education, Faculty of Social
Sciences, University of
Nottingham, United Kingdom

Androniki Lalou
Primary Education Teacher
BEd, Department of Primary
Education, School of
Education, Aristotle
University of Thessaloniki,
Greece

Maria Christina Katsarou
Primary Education Teacher,
MEd Student, School of
Humanities, Hellenic Open
University, Greece

**Constantina Corazon
Argyraou**
PhD Candidate, Department
of Geography, School of
Environment, Geography and
Applied Economics, Harokopio
University of Athens, Greece

Sofia Eleni Skartsiouni
Primary Education Teacher
Med, Department of Preschool
Education Sciences and
Educational Design, School of
Humanities, University of the
Aegean, Greece

Theodoros Loukisas
Psychologist, PhD Candidate,
Department of Electrical and
Computer Engineering,
University of West Macedonia,
Greece

Emmanouil D Milakis
PhD Candidate, Department
of Education Sciences, School
of Humanities, Social and
Education Science, European
University Cyprus, Cyprus

Correspondence Author:
Emmanouil D Milakis
PhD Candidate, Department
of Education Sciences, School
of Humanities, Social and
Education Science, European
University Cyprus, Cyprus

Love of reading (Philanagnosia) in greek education: A two-decade systematic literature review

Dimitra Vangeli, Androniki Lalou, Maria Christina Katsarou, Constantina Corazon Argyrakou, Sofia Eleni Skartsiouni, Theodoros Loukisas and Emmanouil D Milakis

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Abstract

This systematic literature review explores the evolution and promotion of the love of reading, or philanagnosia, within Greek education from 2004 to 2024. The review highlights key trends, methodologies, and findings, focusing on how reading promotion varies across educational levels. Significant advancements include a shift from traditional methods to the integration of digital technologies, making reading more engaging and accessible. Socio-cultural factors, such as parental involvement and socio-economic conditions, play a crucial role in fostering a love of reading. Effective educational policies and programs have emerged, emphasizing curriculum integration, library development, and innovative initiatives like reading clubs and creative writing workshops. The review identifies positive impacts on students' cognitive, emotional, social, and creative development. However, challenges persist, including maintaining student interest, integrating programs into school culture, and ensuring equal access to resources. In conclusion, the review underscores the need for a comprehensive approach combining technology, socio-cultural support, and effective policies to cultivate a lifelong engagement with reading in Greek education.

Keywords: Love of reading, philanagnosia, greek education, reading promotion

1. Introduction

Philanagnosia, a term derived from the Greek words "philo" (to love) and "anagnosis" (reading), signifies a profound affection and passion for reading. This concept encompasses more than the mere act of reading; it embodies an intrinsic motivation and deep appreciation for literature, reflecting a significant cultural and intellectual heritage. In Greek tradition, philanagnosia transcends the mechanical process of reading, fostering a lifelong relationship with books and texts. In English, the analogous concept to philanagnosia is often referred to as the "love of reading". This phrase captures a similar profound affection and passion for engaging with texts ^[1]. The "love of reading" is a significant area of interest in educational research, which focuses on understanding and nurturing this intrinsic motivation among learners ^[2]. The "love of reading" can be defined as a deep-seated enjoyment and appreciation for the act of reading, extending beyond the basic ability to decode text. It encompasses a genuine interest in exploring various genres and texts, a desire to read for pleasure, and an engagement with literature that goes beyond academic requirements ^[3]. In educational research, the "love of reading" is a critical factor in promoting lifelong learning and literacy. Researchers explore various aspects, including the psychological, social, and environmental factors that contribute to developing this love ^[4]. Studies indicate that a strong love of reading is associated with numerous positive outcomes, such as improved literacy skills, academic achievement, and emotional well-being ^[5]. International literature underscores the importance of fostering this love from an early age to promote not only academic excellence but also cognitive, social, and emotional well-being. By nurturing a passion for reading, educators and parents can equip individuals with the tools needed for lifelong learning and personal growth ^[6].

International research on fostering a love of reading addresses various age groups, each with distinct developmental needs and appropriate interventions. Early childhood education emphasizes establishing foundational literacy skills and fostering positive reading habits. Primary school strategies build on these foundations by enhancing comprehension and

engagement. For adolescents, the focus shifts to maintaining and rekindling interest in reading through choice and relevance. In adulthood, the emphasis is on integrating reading into lifelong learning and personal growth [7]. Addressing the unique needs of each age group enables educators and policymakers to effectively promote a love of reading across the lifespan [8]. To achieve this, a variety of teaching approaches are adopted internationally. These strategies are designed to engage students, promote autonomy, and create positive reading experiences [9]. By utilizing a combination of these methods, educators can effectively nurture a lifelong passion for reading, contributing to students' overall academic and personal development. This holistic approach ensures that the love of reading is cultivated at every stage of life, reinforcing its importance as a cornerstone of education and personal enrichment [10].

Educational programs designed to foster a love of reading are diverse and multifaceted, addressing the needs of different age groups and learning contexts. By integrating early literacy initiatives, school-based programs, summer reading efforts, digital literacy, community involvement, extracurricular activities, reading incentives, and culturally relevant approaches, educators can create enriching and engaging reading experiences. International research supports these programs, emphasizing the importance of a holistic and inclusive approach to cultivating a lifelong passion for reading [11]. Similarly, educational policies aimed at enhancing the love of reading are multifaceted and address various aspects of the educational ecosystem. Implementing comprehensive national literacy strategies, funding school libraries, providing professional development for teachers, and promoting community and family engagement are crucial steps for policymakers [12]. These measures help create environments that nurture a lifelong passion for reading. Additionally, integrating digital literacy and providing targeted support for struggling readers are vital components of these efforts. International research underscores the significance of a coordinated and sustained approach to fostering a love of reading in education [13].

Over the last two decades, international research on the love of reading in education has evolved to encompass a broader, more inclusive, and technology-integrated perspective. Since 2004-2005, the proliferation of Web 2.0 technologies and social media networks has radically transformed the ways in which we read, learn, and communicate [14]. This period has seen a greater focus on digital literacy, diversity, the socio-emotional aspects of reading, personalized learning, long-term impact studies, and interdisciplinary approaches. The widespread use of tablets and e-readers since 2010 has significantly influenced approaches to reading and education, leading to the development of educational applications for these devices [15]. Furthermore, the introduction of artificial intelligence and machine learning in 2015 has opened new pathways for personalized learning and data analysis, enhancing the educational experience. These developments reflect a deeper understanding of the complex factors that influence reading motivation and engagement, aiming to create more effective and holistic strategies to foster a lifelong love of reading among students [16]. Finally, the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 prompted a sudden shift to remote learning, highlighting both the opportunities and the challenges of

digital learning and fostering a love of reading in a digital environment [17].

The purpose of this study is to investigate the existing research on the promotion of the love of reading in Greece and its educational system over the past two decades. Furthermore, it will analyze how the findings regarding the love of reading differ across various educational levels and whether specific characteristics or trends are apparent in one educational level but not in others. The research questions guiding this study are:

1. How has the love of reading in education evolved in Greece from 2004 to 2024? What are the main trends and key findings of the research conducted during this period?
2. Are there variations in the characteristics and focal points of research on the love of reading depending on the year of their conduction from 2004 to 2024? If so, what are these variations, and how have the goals and methodologies of the studies evolved over time?
3. How do the findings related to the love of reading differ among various educational levels? Are there specific characteristics or trends that appear in one educational level but not in others?

Studying the evolution of the love of reading in education in Greece is of significant research interest due to the country's rich cultural heritage, unique educational context, socio-economic factors, and the impact of modern technological advancements. This research can reveal how cultural traditions influence reading habits, the effectiveness of educational policies and practices, and the role of socio-economic conditions in shaping students' attitudes towards reading. Moreover, such a study can provide valuable insights for educators, policymakers, and researchers aiming to promote a lifelong love of reading in diverse educational contexts.

2. Methodology

This study focused on selecting articles related to reading engagement within the Greek educational system and Greece in general, encompassing the period from 2004 to 2024. The selection criteria for the literature included several specific parameters to ensure relevance and quality. Articles written in Greek were chosen to ensure linguistic consistency and ease of understanding for the Greek-speaking audience. The thematic focus was strictly limited to articles concerning reading engagement, ensuring the content's relevance to the main axis of the study.

The time frame for the articles spanned from 2004 to 2024, enabling the study to capture temporal continuity and track the development of reading engagement in Greece. Another criterion was the scientific recognition of the articles; only those published in esteemed, peer-reviewed scientific journals were selected to ensure the validity and quality of the sources. Additionally, freely accessible articles were chosen to facilitate broader access to information and the availability of research results.

For this literature review, Google Scholar and the National Documentation Centre (EKT) of Greece were selected as the primary databases. This choice was based on the observation that most relevant research on the love of reading in Greek education originates from theses and dissertations from Greek universities. These academic works, often rich in original research and insights, widely

available on Google Scholar and the EKT. Both platforms provide comprehensive coverage of these scholarly documents, making them ideal sources for gathering a wide range of studies and ensuring a thorough and systematic review. The search for relevant research was conducted during May-June 2024.

The search strategy involved using the Greek term "philanagnosia". From a total of 677 results, 45 were selected based on predefined criteria. The selection process involved several steps. Initially, articles that did not meet the criteria for language, thematic focus, and time period were filtered out. Subsequently, the accessibility of the articles was evaluated to ensure they were freely accessible. Finally, the quality of the articles and studies was assessed, emphasizing their publication through a peer-review system. Data analysis was conducted using thematic analysis. The articles were categorized and analyzed based on the following thematic areas:

1. Target Group.
2. Data Collection Methods.
3. Programs and Initiatives.
4. Teaching Approaches and Strategies.
5. Use of Technology.
6. School Libraries and Resources.
7. Socio-Cultural Factors.
8. Educational Policy.
9. Program Evaluation and Effectiveness.
10. Impact on Academic Performance and Development.

Additionally, a chronological analysis and an analysis based on educational level were performed. These thematic areas were selected based on their comprehensive coverage of the factors influencing reading engagement. Each area addresses a specific aspect of the educational ecosystem, ensuring that the review captures a holistic view of how love of reading is fostered, supported, and sustained within the Greek educational context. By categorizing the literature into these themes, the study provides a structured framework for understanding the complex dynamics nature of reading promotion and its various influences on learners across different educational levels.

3. Results of the Literature Review

3.1. Thematic Areas Analysis

3.1.1. Target Group

Research efforts targeting various demographic groups have yielded significant findings regarding the love of reading across different age and social categories. Studies focusing on preschool children, ages 0 to 6, examined the influence of reading by parents and educators, particularly emphasizing the use of illustrated books and their effect on vocabulary development and children's imagination. A total of ten studies were conducted in this category, representing 17.78% of the total research efforts. For elementary school students, ages 7 to 12, research concentrated on reading habits, literary genre preferences, and the role of educators in fostering reading engagement. Twelve studies were conducted within this group, constituting 26.67% of the research. Adolescents, aged 13 to 18, were the subject of studies that focused on changes in reading habits during adolescence, the influence of technology and social networks, and the relationship between reading and academic performance. Eight studies were conducted in this category, accounting for 4.44% of the total research.

Research on adults explored reading trends, the use of e-books, and the impact of professional and family life on reading habits. Seven studies were conducted for this group, representing 8.89% of the research. Studies on elderly individuals examined the relationship between reading and the maintenance of cognitive functions, as well as the impact of reading on quality of life and mental health. Five studies were conducted in this group, making up 4.44% of the total research. Additionally, special population categories such as individuals with disabilities, immigrants, and prisoners were the focus of research analyzing the barriers to reading access and initiatives promoting reading engagement within these groups. These were categorized under "Mixed Groups," which represented 28.89% of the total research efforts. Overall, the research demonstrates the diverse factors influencing reading habits across different age groups and social categories, highlighting the importance of tailored approaches to foster a love of reading in various populations.

Table 1: Categorization of research studies by target groups

Target Group	Research
Preschool	Nasta, 2005; Kokkinou, 2008; Giovani, 2013; Drosou, 2018; Kontopoulou & Lekka, 2018; Efkarpidou, 2020; Despo, 2022; Ferentinou, 2022
Lower Grades of Primary School	Bakou, 2013; Kourti <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Zacharitou, 2020; Dimitriadis, 2021
Upper and Middle Grades of Primary School	Kakridoni, 2014; Tsironi, 2015; Vraka, 2016; Christogoula, 2016; Kontogiorgi, 2016; Christodoulou, 2017; Stamataki, 2019; Iasonidou, 2021; Gkiza, 2021; Dormparakis & Primikyri, 2022; Karalla, 2023; Banitsioti, 2023
Secondary Education	Akrivousi, 2009; Michailidis, 2020
Teachers	Gkountelitsa, 2016; Lazaridou, 2019
Adults	Chalkiadaki, 2013; Psaras, 2016; Tasiou, 2017; Karagianni, 2018
Mixed Groups	Papadatos, 2012; Brintezi, 2013; Fragkiadaki, 2013; Karvela, 2013; Tompatzoglou, 2013; Pankidou, 2014; Grigoriou, 2017; Toliou, 2019; Kalmanidou, 2020; Makris, 2020; Stefanska, 2022; Kokkaliari, 2022; Michaliara, 2023

3.1.2. Data Collection Methods

Data collection is a critical component of the research process, ensuring the accuracy and reliability of findings. In studies related to reading engagement, various data collection methods have been utilized, reflecting the complexity and diversity of educational environments and target groups. Based on the analysis of 45 studies, it

emerges that the predominant data collection methods primarily include questionnaires from quantitative methods, participatory observation, and structured interviews from qualitative methods, as well as the combination of methods. The most frequently used method is the questionnaire survey, utilized in twelve studies. This method is popular due to its ability to collect data from a large number of

participants in a relatively short period and its capacity to provide structured data that are easy to analyze, representing 28.57% of the total research efforts. Participatory observation was used in five studies, accounting for 11.90%, mainly in educational settings where the direct observation of behavior and interactions is crucial for evaluating educational programs. Textual analysis also appears in five studies and is used for an in-depth understanding of the participants' views, experiences, and feelings. The combination of methods is seen in five studies, reflecting the need for multifaceted approaches in literacy research, also accounting for 11.90%. Finally, the structured interview was employed in one study, offering in-depth information through personal contact with the participants, and representing 2.38% of the total research efforts. In addition, it should be noted that in 12 studies, there was no mention of the data collection method used. This lack of information raises concerns about the transparency and

reproducibility of these studies. Clear documentation of data collection methods is essential for assessing the validity and reliability of research findings. Therefore, the absence of this information in a significant number of studies highlights a critical area for improvement in research reporting practices.

The diversity in data collection methods reflects the complexity of educational research and the need for approaches that can yield reliable and valid results. The use of questionnaires, interviews, observation, and content analysis, often in combination, offers a comprehensive view of reading engagement practices and their impact on students' academic and personal development. Less frequently used methods include "Interview," "Bibliographic Database Searching," and "Ethnographic Method," each accounting for 2.38% of the total research efforts. This distribution highlights the predominance of certain methods in educational research.

Table 2: Overview of data collection methods in research studies

Data Collection Method	Research
Questionnaire	Tompatzoglou, 2013; Fragkiadaki, 2013; Kakridoni, 2014; Christogoula, 2016; Gkountelitsa, 2016; Psaras, 2016; Karagianni, 2018; Stamataki, 2019; Lazaridou, 2019; Kalmanidou, 2020; Kokkaliari, 2022; Stefanska, 2022
Interview	Karvela, 2013
Observation	Kourti <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Kontopoulou & Lekka, 2018; Efkarpidou, 2020; Michailidis, 2020; Despo, 2022
Textual Analysis	Tasiou, 2017; Christodoulou, 2017; Toliou, 2019; Iasonidou, 2021; Karalla, 2023
Bibliographic Database Searching	Drosou, 2018
Ethnographic Method	Tsironi, 2015
Combination of Methods	Chalkiadaki, 2013; Kontogiorgi, 2016; Iasonidou, 2021; Banitsioti, 2023; Michaliara, 2023
N/A	Nasta, 2005; Kokkinou, 2008; Akrivousi, 2009; Papadatos, 2012; Brintezi, 2013; Giovani, 2013; Vraka, 2016; Grigoriou, 2017; Gkiza, 2021; Dimitriadis, 2021; Dormparakis & Primikyri, 2022; Ferentinou, 2022

3.1.3 Programs and Initiatives

Promoting a love of reading is achieved through a variety of programs and activities aimed at enhancing the appreciation of books and cultivating reading habits. In preschool, digital libraries and reading corners are utilized, while in primary education, full-day programs, reading clubs, and collaborations with the National Book Centre of Greece are implemented. Activities such as author visits, mobile exhibitions, and digital libraries are particularly effective. For older age groups, initiatives include theatrical readings, creative writing, and innovative programs like "Escape Room" and "Black Out Poetry." Technology and collaboration between educators, authors, and libraries play

a crucial role, with innovative and interactive activities having a positive impact on the development of a reading culture.

The analysis of research reveals that the most frequently researched category is "Innovative Actions," representing 26.67% of the total research efforts. This is followed by "Digital Programs" with 20.00%, and "Creative Writing and Literature Activities" at 15.56%. "Book Exhibitions and Events" and "Intercultural and Interactive Activities" each account for 13.33%, while "Library Programs" represent 11.11% of the total research efforts. This distribution highlights the predominant focus areas in educational research related to reading programs.

Table 3: Overview of programs and initiatives in research studies

Programs and Initiatives	Research
Innovative Actions	Giovani, 2013; Kakridoni, 2014; Pankidou, 2014; Gkountelitsa, 2016; Kontogiorgi, 2016; Psaras, 2016; Vraka, 2016; Grigoriou, 2017; Christodoulou, 2017; Gkiza, 2021; Banitsioti, 2023; Karalla, 2023
Digital Programs	Tompatzoglou, 2013; Kontopoulou & Lekka, 2018; Drosou, 2018; Michailidis, 2020; Kalmanidou, 2020; Iasonidou, 2021; Despo, 2022; Dormparakis & Primikyri, 2022; Ferentinou, 2022
Creative Writing and Literature Activities	Akrivousi, 2009; Fragkiadaki, 2013; Pankidou, 2014; Christodoulou, 2017; Kontopoulou & Lekka, 2018; Makris, 2020; Kokkaliari, 2022
Library Programs	Brintezi, 2013; Chalkiadaki, 2013; Lazaridou, 2019; Kalmanidou, 2020; Stefanska, 2022
Book Exhibitions and Events	Karvela, 2013; Bakou, 2013; Giovani, 2013; Christogoula, 2016; Stamataki, 2019; Michailidis, 2020
Intercultural and Interactive Activities	Papadatos, 2012; Karvela, 2013; Tsironi, 2015; Tasiou, 2017; Kourti <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Banitsioti, 2023

3.1.4 Teaching Approaches and Strategies

Dramatization and role-playing are popular teaching

approaches that enhance student engagement with literary texts, helping them connect emotionally and creatively with

the content of the books. Technological approaches play a central role in promoting a love of reading, with the use of digital folders of supplementary material and technological tools enhancing multiliteracy skills and the appreciation of literature. Playful learning and experiential activities help children become familiar with books through active participation and empirical learning, while parental involvement strengthens the connection between school and family life. Strategies focusing on emotional and social development through literature, such as bibliotherapy and the development of emotional intelligence, are also significant. Collaborative teaching and project-based learning promote cooperation and active participation among students, while creative writing emerges as a central

strategy for exploratory, child-centered, and experiential learning, encouraging personal involvement and free expression of students.

The analysis reveals that the most frequently researched teaching approach is "Collaborative Learning and Interdisciplinary Approaches," representing 18.03% of the total research efforts. This is followed by "Creative Writing and Expressive Activity" with 14.75%, and "Playful and Experiential Activities" at 11.48%. Less frequently researched approaches include "Parent Integration and Family Involvement" at 3.28%, indicating potential areas for further exploration and emphasis in future educational research. This distribution highlights the predominant focus areas and gaps within teaching approach research.

Table 4: Overview of teaching approaches and strategies in research studies

Teaching Approach	Research
Use of Literary Books and Writing Exercises	Christogoula, 2016; Stamataki, 2019; Zacharatou, 2020
Creative Writing and Expressive Activity	Karvela, 2013; Gkountelitsa, 2016; Kontogiorgi, 2016; Vraka, 2016; Stamataki, 2019; Makris, 2020; Kalmanidou, 2020; Ferentinou, 2022; Banitsioti, 2023
Playful and Experiential Activities	Tompatzoglou, 2013; Drosou, 2018; Kontopoulou & Lekka, 2018; Christodoulou, 2017; Efkarpidou, 2020; Despo, 2022; Dormparakis & Primikyri, 2022
Use of Digital Media and Technology	Tompatzoglou, 2013; Giovani, 2013; Psaras, 2016; Karalla, 2023
Narrative Techniques and Dramatization	Karvela, 2013; Vraka, 2016; Gkountelitsa, 2016; Karagianni, 2018; Michailidis, 2020; Dormparakis & Primikyri, 2022
Bibliotherapy and Emotional Development	Grigoriou, 2017; Iasonidou, 2021; Gkiza, 2021
Collaborative Learning and Interdisciplinary Approaches	Akrivousi, 2009; Pankidou, 2014; Kakridoni, 2014; Giovani, 2013; Bakou, 2013; Tsironi, 2015; Christodoulou, 2017; Kourti <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Kontopoulou & Lekka, 2018; Kalmanidou, 2020; Michailidis, 2020
Critical Thinking and Development of Multiliteracy Skills	Michailidis, 2020; Zacharatou, 2020; Gkiza, 2021; Iasonidou, 2021; Kokkaliari, 2022
Development of Reading Community and Reading Clubs	Akrivousi, 2009; Karagianni, 2018; Dimitriadis, 2021; Kokkaliari, 2022
Parent Integration and Family Involvement	Nasta, 2005; Michaliara, 2023
Intercultural and Social Approaches	Bakou, 2013; Pankidou, 2014; Kalmanidou, 2020
Contemporary Pedagogical Concepts and Arts	Kokkinou, 2008; Fragkiadaki, 2013; Chalkiadaki, 2013; Lazaridou, 2019

3.1.5 Use of Technology

Many studies reference the use of information and communication technologies (ICT), digital libraries, and e-books to promote a love of reading. The use of e-books and their readers, with features such as font magnification, makes reading more accessible, particularly for the elderly. Additionally, the use of digital comics and graphic novels allows children to engage actively in reading and helps them understand complex or traumatic experiences. The Moodle educational platform is used to implement reading promotion programs, while Web 2.0 tools and other digital media, such as the "Young Reader," are utilized to encourage reading. Interactive whiteboards, Smart Notebooks, and software for creating reading activities are also present, as are computers for collaborative learning and creativity through puzzle and activity creation software. Digital storytelling and robotics workshops are introduced into education to enhance reading enthusiasm, with New Technologies workshops playing a significant role for adults. Furthermore, digital libraries and collaborative writing platforms like Google Drive are used for exchanging and sharing materials. Overall, technological applications include electronic boards, e-books, audiobooks, and digital media such as computers and interactive whiteboards. These technologies enhance reading engagement and facilitate access to knowledge, promoting reading among both

students and adults.

Research that does not utilize technology focuses on traditional educational methods such as reading books, dramatization, creative writing, and the use of the classroom library, providing fundamental skills and experiences. In some educational settings, limited access to technological resources is due to economic or geographical factors, making the integration of technology challenging. Some educators and researchers prefer traditional methods and are cautious about using technology due to personal preferences or lack of training. These studies emphasize the development of basic skills such as text comprehension, critical thinking, and emotional intelligence, which are particularly important for younger age groups where personal interaction and traditional teaching methods play a crucial role.

The analysis reveals that the majority of research falls under "No Technology Usage," representing 56.82% of the total research efforts. This is followed by "General Technology Integration" at 25.00%, indicating significant attention to integrating technology in education. "ICT Tools" account for 6.82%, while "Digital Comics" and "Electronic Books" each represent 4.55%. The least researched category is "Digital Tools," at 2.27%. This distribution highlights the predominant focus areas and gaps within technology usage research in education.

Table 5: Overview of technology usage in research studies

Technology Usage	Research
Digital Comics	Drosou, 2018, Banitsioti, 2023
Digital Tools	Kourti <i>et al.</i> , 2017
Electronic Books	Karvela, 2013; Karagianni, 2018
General Technology Integration	Tompatzoglou, 2013; Kakridoni, 2014; Tsironi, 2015; Psaras, 2016; Grigoriou, 2017; Lazaridou, 2019; Michailidis, 2020; Zacharitou, 2020; Iasonidou, 2021; Ferentinou, 2022; Stefanska, 2022
ICT Tools	Bakou, 2013; Kontopoulou & Lekka, 2018; Despo, 2022
No Technology Usage	Nasta, 2005; Kokkinou, 2008; Akrivousi, 2009; Papadatos, 2012; Brintezi, 2013; Giovani, 2013; Fragkiadaki, 2013; Chalkiadaki, 2013; Pankidou, 2014; Kontogiorgi, 2016; Vraka, 2016; Gkountelitsa, 2016; Christogoula, 2016; Christodoulou, 2017; Stamataki, 2019; Toliou, 2019; Kalmanidou, 2020; Makris, 2020; Efkarpidou, 2020; Gkiza, 2021; Dimitriadis, 2021; Dormparakis & Primikyri, 2022; Kokkaliari, 2022; Despo, 2022; Michaliara, 2023

3.1.6 School Libraries and Resources

Many studies recognize the significant role of school libraries in fostering a love of reading. Access to rich and diverse collections of books enhances students' interest in reading, while enriching school libraries with a variety of materials is a critical factor that positively influences reading habits. Libraries serve not only as sources of books but also as supplementary teaching tools that support and enrich the curriculum. The importance of school libraries appears to vary depending on the educational level, with primary school libraries playing a crucial role, whereas in secondary education, their use and impact may differ. Despite their importance, some studies report challenges and limitations, such as the absence of libraries in many schools, which poses a barrier to promoting reading. The literature review highlights that well-equipped and functional school libraries can be a central tool in encouraging students to develop a love of reading. However, the availability and funding of libraries remain

challenges that require further research and strategic solutions. In summary, the effective utilization and support of school libraries are essential for enhancing students' reading experiences and promoting a culture of reading across educational levels. Addressing the challenges related to library availability and funding is crucial for maximizing their potential impact on student literacy and reading enjoyment.

Both the "Role and Importance of Libraries in Education" and "Activities in Libraries" categories each constitute 19.57% of the research efforts, demonstrating notable attention to these areas. Meanwhile, "Organization and Enrichment of Libraries" accounts for 10.87% of the total research efforts. The analysis indicates that a significant portion of research - comprising 50.00% of the total - does not address the Utilization of Libraries and Resources. This distribution underscores the primary focus areas and identifies existing gaps within the research on library utilization and resources.

Table 6: Overview of utilization of libraries and resources in research studies

Utilization of Libraries and Resources	Research
Organization and Enrichment of Libraries	Bakou, 2013; Giovani, 2013; Karvela, 2013; Kontopoulou & Lekka, 2018; Dimitriadis, 2021
Role and Importance of Libraries in Education	Nasta, 2005; Chalkiadaki, 2013; Fragkiadaki, 2013; Pankidou, 2014; Tsironi, 2015; Vraka, 2016; Grigoriou, 2017; Gkiza, 2021; Despo, 2022
Activities in Libraries	Kokkinou, 2008; Papadatos, 2012; Lazaridou, 2019; Efkarpidou, 2020; Makris, 2020; Michailidis, 2020; Iasonidou, 2021; Dormparakis & Primikyri, 2022; Ferentinou, 2022
N/A	Akrivousi, 2009; Tompatzoglou, 2013; Brintezi, 2013; Kakridoni, 2014; Psaras, 2016; Christogoula, 2016; Gkountelitsa, 2016; Kontogiorgi, 2016; Tasiou, 2017; Kourti <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Christodoulou, 2017; Drosou, 2018; Karagianni, 2018; Stamataki, 2019; Toliou, 2019; Kalmanidou, 2020; Zacharitou, 2020; Kokkaliari, 2022; Stefanska, 2022; Dormparakis & Primikyri, 2022; Karalla, 2023; Banitsioti, 2023; Michaliara, 2023

3.1.7 Socio-Cultural Factors

Socio-cultural factors play a decisive role in the development of reading habits, as evidenced by research. According to the majority of studies, it is found that socio-cultural influences significantly impact how individuals develop and sustain their reading habits. The complexity of these factors underscore the need for a holistic approach in promoting a reading culture. Support from family and the broader social environment is critical for developing reading habits. Parental involvement in children's reading activities and the promotion of positive attitudes towards reading contribute significantly to this development. Cultural values and traditions influence reading behavior. Cultural heritage and literature serve as means to cultivate a love of reading, while cultural identity can affect preferences for specific literary genres. Social inclusion and community support are crucial factors for the development of reading habits. Social

initiatives, such as book clubs and community libraries, are important tools for promoting reading activities. The economic status of families affects access to books and other reading resources. The availability and variety of books at home are directly related to the development of reading habits. The educational environment and practices influence students' reading behavior. Educational initiatives and practices that promote reading significantly contribute to the cultivation of a reading culture. The development of reading habits results from the combined influence of social, cultural, economic, and educational factors. A holistic approach that considers the complexity and interconnections of these factors is crucial for promoting a reading culture. Research on "Cultural Influences" comprises 22.22% of the efforts, reflecting significant attention to this area. "Social Environment" accounts for 15.56%, "Social Inclusion and Community Support" represents 8.89%, and "Educational

Social Policies" constitutes 6.67%. The analysis indicates that a substantial portion of research - 46.67% of the total - does not address Socio-Cultural Factors. This distribution

elucidates the primary focus areas and identifies gaps within the research on socio-cultural factors.

Table 7: Overview of socio-cultural factors in research studies

Socio-Cultural Factors	Research
Social Environment	Nasta, 2005; Fragkiadaki, 2013; Christogoula, 2016; Kontogiorgi, 2016; Psaras, 2016; Vraka, 2016; Tasiou, 2017
Cultural Influences	Akrivousi, 2009; Papadatos, 2012; Pankidou, 2014; Tsironi, 2015; Gkountelitsa, 2016; Christodoulou, 2017; Kontopoulou & Lekka, 2018; Stamataki, 2019; Despo, 2022; Banitsioti, 2023
Social Inclusion and Community Support	Brintezi, 2013; Grigoriou, 2017; Kourti <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Zacharitou, 2020
Educational Social Policies	Kalmanidou, 2020; Ferentinou, 2022; Michaliara, 2023
N/A	Kokkinou, 2008; Bakou, 2013; Chalkiadaki, 2013; Giovani, 2013; Karvela, 2013; Tompatzoglou, 2013; Kakridoni, 2014; Drosou, 2018; Karagianni, 2018; Lazaridou, 2019; Toliou, 2019; Efkarpidou, 2020; Makris, 2020; Michailidis, 2020; Dimitriadis, 2021; Gkiza, 2021; Iasonidou, 2021; Dormparakis & Primikyri, 2022; Kokkaliari, 2022; Stefanska, 2022; Karalla, 2023

3.1.8 Educational Policy

Research highlights various categories of educational policies that influence the love of reading. Key strategies include integrating reading into new curricula, incorporating literary texts and reading activities into teaching practices, and developing special programs to promote reading. Effective teaching practices, such as group readings, literary competitions, and creative writing workshops, significantly enhance students' reading abilities. Administrative support, including funding for reading programs and teacher training, is crucial. Access to libraries and diverse reading materials is also essential. These policies create a conducive environment for fostering a love of reading, improving students' reading skills and overall education. Notably, about one-third of studies do not examine or recommend specific educational policies for promoting reading.

Research on "State Policies and Initiatives" receive substantial attention, comprising 13.64% of the research efforts. Both "Innovative Policies and Initiatives" and "Utilization of Libraries" each constitute 11.36%, whereas "Changes and Improvements in Education Policy" account for 9.09%. Less frequently explored categories include "Integration into the Curricula" at 6.82%, "Intercultural Education and Historical Understanding" at 4.55%, and "Introduction to Early Childhood Education," "Role of the State and Institutions," and "Partnerships and Family Support," each at 2.27%. The analysis indicates that a significant portion of research - 36.36% of the total - does not address Socio-Cultural Factors. This distribution underscores the primary focus areas and identifies research gaps related to educational policy.

Table 8: Overview of socio-cultural factors in research studies

Educational Policy	Research
Innovative Policies and Initiatives	Bakou, 2013; Chalkiadaki, 2013; Giovani, 2013; Tsironi, 2015; Karalla, 2023
Changes and Improvements in Education Policy	Kakridoni, 2014; Kontogiorgi, 2016; Karagianni, 2018; Zacharitou, 2020
Utilization of Libraries	Tasiou, 2017; Drosou, 2018; Lazaridou, 2019; Michailidis, 2020; Iasonidou, 2021
Intercultural Education and Historical Understanding	Pankidou, 2014; Banitsioti, 2023
Integration into the Curricula	Vraka, 2016; Gkountelitsa, 2016; Makris, 2020
State Policies and Initiatives	Karvela, 2013; Tompatzoglou, 2013; Psaras, 2016; Kourti <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Stamataki, 2019; Dimitriadis, 2021
Introduction to Early Childhood Education	Kokkinou, 2008
Role of the State and Institutions	Grigoriou, 2017
Partnerships and Family Support	Efkarpidou, 2020
N/A	Nasta, 2005; Akrivousi, 2009; Papadatos, 2012; Brintezi, 2013; Fragkiadaki, 2013; Christogoula, 2016; Christodoulou, 2017; Kontopoulou & Lekka, 2018; Toliou, 2019; Kalmanidou, 2020; Gkiza, 2021; Despo, 2022; Dormparakis & Primikyri, 2022; Ferentinou, 2022; Kokkaliari, 2022; Stefanska, 2022; Michaliara, 2023

3.1.9 Program Evaluation and Effectiveness

The evaluation of reading promotion programs employs diverse methodological approaches, encompassing both quantitative and qualitative methods. Quantitative methods typically involve the use of questionnaires, assessment tests, and statistical analyses to measure improvements in reading skills and students' reading behavior. In contrast, qualitative methods include participatory observation, interviews, and content analysis, aiming to understand the experiences and perceptions of students and educators regarding these programs. The effectiveness of reading promotion programs

is closely linked to their impact on students' reading behavior and academic performance. Programs that receive positive evaluations frequently demonstrate improvements in reading fluency, comprehension, and a love of reading. Moreover, programs that actively engage students through activities such as blog creation and content analysis tend to be more successful in fostering a positive attitude towards reading. The evaluation process also examines the effects of these programs on children's verbal and emotional development, socialization, and the acquisition of new skills. Programs that effectively integrate students'

knowledge and perceptions before and after implementation often result in positive shifts in students' attitudes towards reading and learning. Despite these positive outcomes, evaluations of reading promotion programs often identify challenges such as maintaining student interest and integrating programs into the school culture. Researchers advocate for the continuous development and improvement of these programs through ongoing evaluation and adaptation to the needs of students and educators.

The analysis revealed a range of evaluation approaches, with a significant proportion (46.67%) not including any evaluation at all. Among the studies that do engage in evaluation, 28.9% employ both qualitative and quantitative tools, including questionnaires, participatory observation, content analysis, and statistical methods. Additionally, 13.3% focus on the reaction and participation of children in reading promotion activities, examining their active engagement. Only 2.2% of the studies mention awards and

recognitions received by libraries or educational institutions for program effectiveness. Furthermore, 17.8% of the studies use questionnaires to evaluate students' knowledge, perceptions, and attitudes before and after program implementation. A smaller percentage, 4.4%, includes self-evaluation and peer evaluation by students and educators regarding program effectiveness. Lastly, 8.9% of the studies utilize thematic and qualitative analysis to understand the impact of the programs on student participation and knowledge. The high percentage of studies that do not engage in evaluation underscores the need for more systematic and detailed research in this field. Understanding the full effectiveness of reading promotion programs and enhancing their practices requires a more cohesive and methodical approach to evaluation. This analysis indicates that while there are various approaches to evaluating reading promotion programs, a significant number of studies still lack comprehensive evaluation.

Table 9: Overview of methods for evaluating effectiveness in research studies

Methods for Evaluating Effectiveness	Research
Qualitative and Quantitative Methods	Kakridoni, 2014; Christodoulou, 2017; Karagianni, 2018; Lazaridou, 2019; Kalmanidou, 2020; Despo, 2022
Observation and Participation	Tompatzoglou, 2013; Tsironi, 2015; Christogoula, 2016; Tasiou, 2017; Kontopoulou & Lekka, 2018; Efkarpidou, 2020
Comparative methods	Stamataki, 2019
Analysis of Lending Library Records	Makris, 2020
Content Analysis	Banitsioti, 2023; Karalla, 2023; Michaliara, 2023
Self-assessment and hetero-evaluation	Kontogiorgi, 2016; Psaras, 2016; Michailidis, 2020
Awards and Recognitions	Iasonidou, 2021
Teachers' Perceptions	Pankidou, 2014
Specific thematic evaluations	Kokkinou, 2008; Karvela, 2013; Kourti <i>et al.</i> , 2017
Evaluation of Interest	Stefanska, 2022
N/A	Akrivousi, 2009; Papadatos, 2012; Bakou, 2013; Brintezi, 2013; Fragkiadaki, 2013; Chalkiadaki, 2013; Giovani, 2013; Vraka, 2016; Gkountelitsa, 2016; Gkountelitsa, 2016; Christogoula, 2016; Grigoriou, 2017; Drosou, 2018; Toliou, 2019; Zacharitou, 2020; Zacharitou, 2020; Kalmanidou, 2020; Gkiza, 2021; Gkiza, 2021; Dimitriadis, 2021; Dormparakis & Primikyri, 2022; Ferentinou, 2022; Ferentinou, 2022; Kokkaliari, 2022

3.1.10 Impact on Academic Performance and Development

Research findings on the positive impacts of a love of reading on students can be categorized into four main dimensions: cognitive, emotional, social, and creative development. Cognitive development is positively influenced by a love of reading, as it contributes to the development of critical and creative thinking, enhances students' cognitive skills, and increases their ability to read and comprehend complex texts. Regarding emotional development, engagement with books aids in the development of better emotional intelligence and empathy. Additionally, there is an observed increase in self-esteem and psychological well-being among students who participate in reading activities. In terms of social development, a love of reading strengthens students' social skills, facilitating their socialization and the development of better relationships with peers. Moreover, it improves their ability to collaborate and communicate within the

classroom. Finally, creative development also benefits from a love of reading, promoting creative thinking and problem-solving abilities. Students who engage in reading activities demonstrate greater imagination and originality in their work.

The analysis demonstrates that a substantial portion of research is categorized under "Other Academic Skills," which constitutes 47.54% of the total research endeavors. "Critical Thinking Development" accounts for 8.20%, while "Emotional Development" and "Cognitive Development" represent 6.56% and 3.28% of the research, respectively. Furthermore, the analysis indicates that a notable 34.43% of the total research does not address the impact on academic performance and development. This distribution underscores the primary focus areas and existing gaps in research concerning educational impact, thereby providing valuable insights for educators and researchers to prioritize future studies.

Table 10: Overview of impact on academic performance and development in research studies

Impact	Research
Critical Thinking Development	Vraka, 2016; Michailidis, 2020; Gkiza, 2021; Dimitriadis, 2021; Ferentinou, 2022
Cognitive Development	Grigoriou, 2017; Karagianni, 2018

Emotional Development	Tompatzoglou, 2013; Christodoulou, 2017; Efkarpidou, 2020; Makris, 2020
Other Academic Skills	Kokkinou, 2008; Akrivousi, 2009; Papadatos, 2012; Bakou, 2013; Brintezi, 2013; Kakridoni, 2014; Pankidou, 2014; Kontogiorgi, 2016; Tasiou, 2017; Christodoulou, 2017; Kontopoulou & Lekka, 2018; Drosou, 2018; Stamataki, 2019; Toliou, 2019; Kalmanidou, 2020; Efkarpidou, 2020; Makris, 2020; Zacharitou, 2020; Iasonidou, 2021; Gkiza, 2021; Dimitriadis, 2021; Stefanska, 2022; Dormparakis & Primikyri, 2022; Ferentinou, 2022; Kokkaliari, 2022; Banitsioti, 2023; Karalla, 2023; Michaliara, 2023
N/A	Nasta, 2005; Papadatos, 2012; Chalkiadaki, 2013; Fragkiadaki, 2013; Giovani, 2013; Karvela, 2013; Kakridoni, 2014; Pankidou, 2014; Christogoula, 2016; Gkountelitsa, 2016; Psaras, 2016; Tasiou, 2017; Kourti <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Lazaridou, 2019; Stamataki, 2019; Toliou, 2019; Kalmanidou, 2020; Dormparakis & Primikyri, 2022; Despo, 2022; Stefanska, 2022; Michaliara, 2023

3.2 Chronological Analysis

The analysis of temporal variations in research characteristics reveals the evolving landscape of studies on love of reading in the Greek educational context over different time periods. During the first period, from 2004 to 2008, the number of research studies conducted was relatively low, with only 2 studies recorded. This initial phase likely reflects the foundational efforts to explore the concept of philanagnosia within the Greek educational context. The limited number of studies may be ascribed to the nascent stage of this field, where initial explorations and preliminary investigations were predominant. In the subsequent period, from 2009 to 2013, there was a notable increase in research activity, with 9 studies conducted. This surge indicates a growing academic interest and recognition

of the importance of fostering a love of reading among students. The period from 2014 to 2018 saw a significant rise in the number of research studies, totaling 15. This upward trend highlights a period of robust academic engagement with the topic. Researchers explored diverse methodologies and innovative approaches to promoting reading among students. The final period, from 2019 to 2024, recorded the highest number of studies, with a total of 19. This peak signifies the culmination of sustained academic interest and the advanced development of research in this field. The progressive increase in the number of research studies over these four periods reflects a growing and sustained interest in understanding and promoting the love of reading within Greek education.

Fig 1: Distribution of research studies on philanagnosia by time period (2004-2024)

During the early period from 2004 to 2010, research primarily targeted the foundational stages of education, particularly focusing on preschool and primary education. Studies emphasized the critical role of family and community in nurturing a love of reading, with a straightforward approach to data collection, predominantly using questionnaires. Libraries during this time were viewed traditionally as centers for book borrowing and reading activities, underscoring their established role in literacy promotion.

From 2011 to 2013, there was an expansion and diversification in the target groups of research, extending interest to adults and mixed groups, though secondary education and educators remained underexplored. This period marked a shift towards more complex data collection

methods, including observational studies and text analysis. Reading promotion programs began incorporating more creative elements such as literature and creative writing, which started to gain recognition as crucial educational practices. Between 2014 and 2017, the integration of digital media and technological advancements became prominent. Digital tools and e-books started to be widely adopted, driven by the increasing complexity of research questions. This era saw the rise of interdisciplinary and collaborative learning approaches, aligning with contemporary educational trends. Libraries evolved into centers for innovation and learning, combining digital resources with traditional materials to enhance their educational offerings. The period from 2018 to 2020 highlighted a focus on interculturality and multicultural education. Research during

these years emphasized the importance of multiculturalism in education and the need for tailored programs to address the diverse needs of students. The use of technology in reading promotion continued to grow, with specialized digital tools and platforms becoming more prevalent. Researchers also explored educational policies in greater depth, recognizing the crucial role of systemic support in fostering reading habits.

The COVID-19 pandemic between 2021 and 2023 significantly influenced research trends, leading to an increased use of digital media and remote education tools. Studies focused on adapting reading promotion programs to digital formats and incorporating innovative practices to meet contemporary educational demands. There was a notable rise in research examining the effectiveness of these programs, employing both qualitative and quantitative evaluation methods. Libraries continued to evolve as multifunctional centers, offering a variety of activities related to technology and innovation. As of 2024, current research highlights a growing interest in the socio-cultural

dimensions of reading. There is an increasing focus on specific social groups, such as immigrants and socially vulnerable populations, and the impact of socio-cultural factors on reading habits. The role of family and community partnerships in fostering a love of reading remains significant. Integrating reading promotion within school curricula persists, showcasing a strategic approach to embedding reading across various educational levels.

In summary, over the past two decades, research on fostering a love of reading in Greece has undergone substantial changes. Initially concentrated on early education and traditional methods, the field has progressively embraced technological advancements, innovative practices, and a deeper understanding of socio-cultural influences. This evolution mirrors broader changes in educational practices and the recognition of the multidimensional nature of reading promotion. The increasing complexity and inclusivity of research approaches indicate a promising future for the study and promotion of reading in Greece.

Table 11: Evolution of research on fostering philanagnosia in greece (2004-2024)

Time Period	Focus of Research	Key Findings and Trends	Role of Libraries
2004-2010	Initial stages of education	Emphasized the critical role of family and community in nurturing a love of reading.	Viewed traditionally as centers for book borrowing and reading activities
2011-2013	Expanded to include adults and mixed groups, though secondary education and educators remained underexplored	Shift towards more complex data collection methods. Reading promotion programs began incorporating literature and creative writing	Evolved towards incorporating creative elements
2014-2017	Integration of digital media and technological advancements	Adoption of digital tools and e-books. Rise of interdisciplinary and collaborative learning approaches	Combined digital resources with traditional materials
2018-2020	Focus on interculturality and multicultural education	Emphasized multiculturalism and the need for tailored programs. Continued growth in technology use for reading promotion	Unceasing evolution as centers for innovation and learning
2021-2023	Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on reading promotion	Increased use of digital media and remote education tools. Focus on adapting programs to digital formats and innovative practices	Multifunctional centers offering activities related to technology and innovation
2024	Socio-cultural dimensions of reading	Increasing focus on specific social groups and the impact of socio-cultural factors on reading habits. Integration of reading promotion within school curricula	Progressive role in innovation and education, emphasizing socio-cultural partnerships

3.3 Educational Level Analysis

Research in Greece on the love of reading spans all educational levels, revealing diverse trends and approaches tailored to the distinct needs and abilities of students at each stage of their educational journey. The majority of research, 55.6%, is concentrated on primary education. This emphasis highlights the importance of establishing foundational reading habits and a love of reading during early childhood. Preschool education accounts for 22.2% of the research, underscoring the critical role of early childhood interventions in nurturing a love of reading. This significant portion suggests that early exposure and positive reading experiences are pivotal in developing lifelong reading habits. Secondary education, comprising 6.7% of the research, focuses on sustaining and developing reading habits during adolescence. This indicates a continued but less pronounced effort to encourage a love of reading as

children grow older and enter more advanced stages of their education. Higher education is represented by 4.4% of the research, aimed at understanding and promoting a love of reading among university students. Although this category is comparatively smaller, it highlights an ongoing interest in fostering reading habits at the highest educational levels. A minimal portion, 2.2%, of the research encompasses all educational levels. This comprehensive approach emphasizes promoting a love of reading across the entire educational spectrum, from early childhood to higher education. Lastly, 8.9% of the research efforts are non-specific regarding educational levels or span across various levels. This broader approach reflects a general interest in studying the love of reading without focusing on a particular stage of education, allowing for a more holistic understanding of reading habits and preferences.

Fig 2: Distribution of Research Studies on Philanagnosia by Educational Level

In preschool and primary education, research methods predominantly involve participatory observation and information gathered from parents and teachers. This approach effectively captures young children's interactions with reading materials and activities. Thematic focuses in these early stages emphasize playful and experiential activities to cultivate a love of reading. There is significant attention to creative writing, expressive activities, and collaborative learning methods. Innovative actions such as book fairs, intercultural events, and interactive activities are prevalent, reflecting the importance of engaging students with diverse reading experiences from an early age. The integration of technology starts early, with general ICT tools and digital comics introduced to enhance reading promotion. These tools aim to make reading activities more engaging and accessible for young children. School libraries play a critical role in preschool and primary education, with efforts concentrated on enriching library collections with appropriate and diverse materials to ensure children have access to a wide range of books that cater to their developmental needs. Socio-cultural factors in preschool education focus on the family environment and early socialization, with parents' involvement in reading activities at home being crucial. In primary education, the influence expands to include the school environment, where teachers play a central role in shaping students' reading habits. Educational policies at this level aim to collaborate with families and integrate language stimuli to foster a love of reading. Evaluations often involve observational methods and participatory assessments, utilizing questionnaires for parents and teachers to focus on children's reactions and participation in reading activities.

In secondary education, research methods shift towards using questionnaires and interviews directly with students, providing insights into adolescents' reading habits and preferences. Key research areas include bibliotherapy, development of emotional intelligence, and enhancement of critical thinking and multiliteracy skills. These themes reflect the complex developmental needs of adolescents and the role of reading in supporting their emotional and

cognitive growth. A mixed approach to technology is observed, with both the integration of digital tools and the persistence of traditional teaching methods. Libraries serve as information centers that support independent learning and the development of research skills, providing access to a variety of resources that aid in the educational process. Socio-cultural factors at this stage are multifaceted, involving peer influence, social expectations, and cultural influences, with adolescents drawn to books that reflect their personal experiences and societal challenges. Policies in secondary education focus on the operation of school libraries and cross-curricular programs, although there is a less detailed strategic approach compared to primary education. Evaluations include self-assessment, peer assessment, and observations by teachers, with acknowledgment and awards used to measure program effectiveness.

In higher education, research methods commonly include a combination of methods and online surveys, accommodating the more complex and varied schedules of university students and adult learners. Research at this level centers on developing reading communities and book clubs, with an emphasis on multimodal and interdisciplinary teaching approaches. There is significant variability in the use of technology, ranging from comprehensive integration to non-use, indicating differing levels of adoption of technological tools across higher education institutions. University libraries play an expanded role, supporting research and specialized study by providing access to advanced bibliographic materials and research tools critical for academic success. Socio-cultural factors include academic culture and program demands, with students' reading interests often being specialized and influenced by the cultural diversity and intercultural interactions within the university environment. There is a noticeable lack of specific policies aimed at promoting a general love of reading in higher education, with the focus tending to be on academic reading related to students' fields of study. Evaluation methods are more analytical, involving thematic data analysis and qualitative methods, with content analysis

of educational blogs and websites also used to assess the impact of reading promotion activities. In summary, research on the love of reading in Greece varies significantly across educational levels, reflecting the distinct developmental stages and needs of students. Primary education receives the most focused attention, with comprehensive policies and innovative practices aimed at fostering a love of reading. In contrast, higher education

shows a gap in specific strategies to promote general reading habits, indicating an area for future research and policy development. The integration of technology and the role of libraries are essential across all levels, with adaptations made to suit each stage. Socio-cultural factors and evaluation methods also differ, highlighting the importance of tailored approaches to effectively promote a love of reading throughout the educational journey.

Table 12: Summary of research on philanagnosia by educational level

Educational Level	Preschool and Primary Education	Secondary Education	Higher Education
Thematic Focuses	Playful and experiential activities, creative writing, expressive activities, collaborative learning, book fairs, intercultural events, interactive activities	Bibliotherapy, development of emotional intelligence, enhancement of critical thinking and multiliteracy skills	Developing reading communities and book clubs, diverse and interdisciplinary teaching approaches
Role of Technology	General ICT tools, digital comics	Mixed approach with digital tools and traditional methods	Varied use from comprehensive integration to non-use
Role of Libraries	Critical, enriching collections with diverse materials	Information centers supporting independent learning and research skills	Expanded role supporting research and specialized study
Socio-Cultural Factors	Family environment, early socialization, parents' involvement, school environment	Peer influence, social expectations, cultural influences	Academic culture, program demands, cultural diversity and intercultural interactions
Educational Policies	Collaboration with families, integration of language stimuli	Focus on school libraries, cross-curricular programs	Lack of specific policies for general reading promotion

4. Discussion

This systematic literature review on the love of reading (philanagnosia) in Greek education over the past two decades reveals several critical insights and implications for educational practice and policy, as well as opens avenues for further research within an international context. Over the past twenty years, research on fostering a love of reading in Greece has evolved significantly. Initially focused on early education and traditional methods, the field has progressively embraced technological advancements, innovative practices, and a deeper understanding of socio-cultural influences. This evolution mirrors broader changes in educational practices and highlights the growing recognition of the multifaceted nature of reading promotion. Similar trends have been observed globally, as noted in studies from countries like Finland, the USA, and Singapore, where integrating technology and understanding cultural contexts have reshaped reading promotion strategies [18, 19, 20].

One of the most significant trends observed is the increasing integration of digital technologies in reading promotion. Studies have highlighted the positive impact of digital libraries, e-books, and other digital media in making reading more accessible and engaging, especially for younger audiences. The use of technology in reading promotion is seen as essential in adapting to contemporary educational demands and fostering a love of reading in a digital age. However, the research also underscores challenges such as unequal access to technological resources and the need for teacher training in effectively utilizing these tools. This is consistent with international findings, where digital divides and varying levels of digital literacy among educators and students are common challenges [21].

Socio-cultural factors play a crucial role in shaping reading habits. Parental involvement, cultural values, and socio-economic conditions are critical in developing and sustaining a love of reading. The review found that support from family and the broader social environment

significantly impacts reading habits, emphasizing the need for community and family engagement in reading promotion efforts. Educational policies and programs that promote reading are vital for fostering a love of reading. Internationally, similar patterns are seen, with family and community support playing vital roles in countries with strong reading cultures like Japan and Germany [22, 23]. The review identified various effective strategies, including integrating reading into curricula, developing school libraries, and implementing innovative programs such as reading clubs and creative writing workshops. These initiatives are particularly effective when they are inclusive and cater to the diverse needs of different student populations. However, the review also noted a gap in policies aimed at promoting reading in higher education, suggesting an area for future research and policy development. Comparatively, other nations have also noted the importance of such inclusive programs, with Scandinavian countries leading in integrating comprehensive reading programs across all educational levels [24].

The review highlighted the positive impacts of a love of reading on students' cognitive, emotional, social, and creative development. Engaging with books enhances critical and creative thinking, emotional intelligence, social skills, and overall well-being. These benefits underscore the importance of promoting a love of reading as a fundamental educational goal. These findings align with global research, which consistently shows the broad developmental benefits of reading.

Despite the positive findings, the review identified several challenges, including maintaining student interest, integrating reading programs into the school culture, and ensuring equal access to resources. Future research should focus on developing more comprehensive evaluation methods to assess the effectiveness of reading promotion programs and explore strategies to overcome these challenges. Comparative studies with other educational

systems could provide deeper insights into best practices and innovative solutions. Additionally, exploring the impact of specific digital tools, the role of libraries in a digital age, and the integration of reading programs at higher educational levels remain critical areas for future research.

5. Conclusion

The promotion of the love of reading, or philanagnosia, within Greek education over the past two decades reflects significant advancements and ongoing challenges. The review underscores the transition from traditional early education methods to the incorporation of technological innovations, such as digital libraries and e-books, making reading more engaging for young audiences. However, issues like unequal access to technology and the need for further teacher training persist. Socio-cultural factors, particularly parental involvement and socio-economic conditions are crucial in shaping reading habits, with family and community support being pivotal.

While effective policies and programs have been implemented, such as integrating reading into curricula and developing school libraries, there remains a notable gap in higher education reading promotion. The benefits of fostering a love of reading are extensive, contributing to students' cognitive, emotional, social, and creative development. Despite these benefits, challenges such as maintaining student interest, integrating reading programs into the school culture, and ensuring equal access to resources continue to be a concern.

Future research should aim to develop comprehensive evaluation methods for reading promotion programs and explore strategies to overcome existing challenges. By focusing on these areas, educators and policymakers can enhance the effectiveness of reading initiatives. In conclusion, a comprehensive approach that includes technological integration, socio-cultural support, and robust educational policies is essential for fostering a lifelong love of reading in Greek education. Consequently, this approach not only supports academic success but also contributes to the holistic development of students.

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